

How to Polish a Diamond: Strengthening Scholar-led Journals in the Netherlands

Authors: Femke Holwerda, Juliana Costa Pitanguy and Maria Constantin

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Reviewed by: Susanne van Rijn, Chiara Livio

Short summary

This report summarizes the results of the workshop given during the [National Open Science Festival](#), held at Maastricht University on 22nd October 2024. The workshop consisted of a short ten-minute presentation of the program “Strengthening Diamond Open Access (OA) in the Netherlands” followed by three breakout sessions.

The outcome of three break-out rooms can be found below. The sections in **green** represents what the participants identified as **very important** to achieve and **easy to implement** while the sections in **blue** represent describes what is **very important** to achieve but **hard to implement**.

We would like to take to all participants of the workshop for their valuable input.

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Break out room 1: What would a national publishing platform for journals need to be successful?

Break-out room lead by Susanne van Rijn

To create a successful national publishing platform, several factors should be addressed:

1. **Quality and Prestige:** The platform must emphasize high-quality publications with open science values and up-to-date publishing support to attract journals and establish credibility.
2. **Experimental Infrastructure:** Given the diverse needs of journals, a flexible, experimental publishing infrastructure is essential to accommodate various formats and functionalities.
3. **Broad Dissemination:** Searching for publications is mostly done through databases, not by visiting journal websites. Qualitative metadata and various dissemination strategies are crucial to have an impact.
4. **Impact-Driven Start with Textbooks:** Starting with e-textbooks is a good point as textbooks often reach broader audiences.
5. **User-Friendly Systems for Editors:** No single system currently meets all editors' needs, so a user-friendly and adaptable interface is crucial.

Breakout room 2: How can we improve the visibility and impact of Diamond OA?

Break-out room lead by Maria Constantin

To improve the visibility and impact of Diamond Open Access (OA), the following steps are essential:

1. **Enhanced Communication and Visibility of Diamond OA journals:** Develop an overview of existing Diamond OA journals and track publications by institution, ideally managed at a national level with dedicated marketing support. Inform librarians about the Diamond OA publication culture at their institutions and encourage financial contribution towards those journals or platforms. Educate researchers about quality Diamond OA journals in their field.
2. **Quality Improvement and Indexing:** Focus on elevating the quality of Diamond OA journals and ensuring they are properly archived and indexed for greater discoverability.
3. **Attract Top Editors and Authors:** Building prestige in Diamond OA requires long-term efforts to attract high-profile editors and authors, which will enhance the journal's reputation.
4. Encourage or support [Collective actions in Science Diamond](#) in various fields.
5. Support researchers towards flipping journals to Diamond OA

6. Making recommendations for policy on Diamond OA at library, university and national level can lead to more authors and thereby increase the visibility of Diamond OA.

Breakout room 3: How can we encourage researchers to publish in Diamond OA venues?

Break-out room lead by Chiara Livio

To encourage researchers to publish in Diamond Open Access (OA) venues, several strategies and considerations are essential:

1. **Increase Awareness of Diamond OA via Training and Promotion:** By creating high-quality sessions on how to make “good” publishing choices.
2. **Emphasize Quality and Sustainability:** Researchers value journals with strong editorial boards, long-term sustainability, and international or local relevance. Promoting Diamond OA journals with these attributes can boost credibility.
3. **Institutional Recognition and Rewards Incentives:** Researchers seek recognition which normally they get but publishing in established journals. Changing Institutional policies to promote Diamond OA can change the perspective of researchers on where to publish.
4. **Support Infrastructure and Diamond OA Costs:** Investment in infrastructure and covering associated costs for researchers and societies are crucial, particularly for small societies, which are well-positioned to transition to Diamond OA.
5. **Collaboration and Strategy for Visibility:** Bringing like-minded editors and researchers together to innovate within Diamond OA can help build journals’ reputations. Clear visibility strategies for Diamond OA journals will also aid in attracting submissions.
6. **Budget Allocation for Community-Led Initiatives:** Encouraging community-driven funding models, such as KU Leuven's approach, can provide sustainable support for Diamond OA.